

Supplementary information to

Effect of milking interval and lactation stage on withdrawal period:
exemplified with a bovine oxytetracycline lactation physiologically based
kinetic model

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SI Model code

- Milk volume model code

SI Tables

Table S1. The varied parameters in the Monte Carlo simulations with the adapted PBK model including the novel milk volume model, used to simulate the different scenarios.

Parameter description		Parameter name in model	Unit	Lactation stage	Input mean	Input CV%	Output mean	Output 1st percentile	Output 99th percentile
	Cardiac output	CO ^a	L/h/kg	All	5.45	27	5.4	2.8	9.5
	Haematocrit	hmtc ^a	-	All	0.35	8.7	0.35	0.29	0.43
BW fraction	Blood	fVblood ^a	-	All	0.0452	20	0.045	0.027	0.07
	Lung	fVlung ^a	-	All	0.007	20	0.0071	0.0044	0.011
	Muscle	fVmuscle ^a	-	All	0.361	32	0.34	0.16	0.54
	Kidneys	fVkidneys ^a	-	All	0.0025	20	0.0025	0.0015	0.0038
	Liver	fVliver ^a	-	All	0.0131	21	0.013	0.008	0.021
	Fat	fVadipose ^a	-	All	0.1321	50	0.12	0.044	0.29
	Udder	fVudder ^a	-	All	0.032	25	0.032	0.018	0.056
	GIntestines	fVGIntestines ^a	-	All	0.0216	25	0.021	0.012	0.035
	Intestines	fVintestines ^a	-	All	0.0137	25	0.014	0.0073	0.023
	Bones	fVbones ^a	-	All	0.0866	17	0.086	0.058	0.13
	Brain	fVbrain ^a	-	All	0.0007	14	0.0007	0.0005	0.00097
	Heart	fVheart ^a	-	All	0.0037	19	0.0037	0.0023	0.0056
	Pancreas	fVpancreas ^a	-	All	0.0008	25	0.0008	0.00045	0.0013
Spleen	fVspleen ^a	-	All	0.0016	25	0.0016	0.00088	0.0027	
CO fraction	Muscle	fQmuscle ^a	-	All	0.18	32	0.17	0.077	0.33
	Kidneys	fQkidneys ^a	-	All	0.07	90	0.059	0.0088	0.2
	Liver	fQliver ^a	-	All	0.51	33	0.41	0.22	0.63
	Fat	fQadipose ^a	-	All	0.074	24	0.073	0.042	0.12
	Udder	fQudder ^a	-	All	0.13	46	0.12	0.042	0.27
Partition coefficient	Muscle	Kmuscle ^a	-	All	0.9	20	0.91	0.56	1.4
	Lung	Klung ^a	-	All	2.3	20	2.3	1.4	3.6
	Kidneys	Kkidneys ^a	-	All	6.62	25	6.7	3.4	12
	Liver	Kliver ^a	-	All	1.87	25	1.8	1	3.2
	Fat	Kadipose ^a	-	All	0.09	47	0.089	0.027	0.23
Absorption	Intramuscular absorption rate	kIM ^a	h ⁻¹	All	0.171	22	1	1	1
	Intramuscular bioavailability	FIM ^a	-	All	0.885	11	0.17	0.1	0.27
Plasma	Fraction unbound	fup ^a	-	All	0.81	3	0.86	0.69	0.99
	Albumin	Albp ^a	g/L	All	30.81	6	0.81	0.76	0.86
Extracellular water	Albumin	AlbEW ^a	g/L	All	14.52	22	31	27	35
Intracellular water	Calcium	IWcalcium ^a	g/L	All	0.0114	30	15	8.7	24
	Magnesium	IWmagnesium ^a	g/L	All	0.024	30	0.011	0.0054	0.022
Excretion	Plasma clearance	CLplasma ^a	L/h/kg	All	0.09	24	0.024	0.012	0.047
	Capillary radius	r ^a	mm	All	0.0025	30	0.089	0.051	0.15
Milk	Calcium	MilkCalcium ^a	g/L	All	0.08	13	0.0025	0.0012	0.0046
	Magnesium	MilkMagnesium ^a	g/L	All	0.018	5	0.079	0.056	0.11

Transfer rate from alveoli to cistern	kAlv2Cis ^b	h ⁻¹	All	0.099	30	0.018	0.016	0.02
Minimum volume alveoli	AlvMin ^b	L	All	1.5	30	0.097	0.048	0.18
Maximum volume alveoli	AlvMax ^b	L	Early	12	30	1.5	0.72	2.9
			Mid	10	30	12	6.3	24
			Late	11	30	10	5.3	20
Maximum volume cistern	CisMax ^b	L	Early	6.4	30	11	5.5	20
			Mid	5.9	30	6.3	3.2	12
			Late	8	30	5.9	2.9	11
Production rate	kmilkprod ^b	h ⁻¹	Early	0.61	30	8	3.9	15
			Mid	0.4	30	0.6	0.29	1.1
			Late	0.27	30	0.4	0.18	0.76

a: parameter varied as in Tardiveau model; b: new parameter in Monte Carlo simulation

Table S2. The yield per milking and daily yield for the 1000 simulated cows. The milk volume model was used for this simulation, where the milking interval, milking frequency, and all estimated parameters were randomly selected for 5000 individuals.

Stage	Yield per milking (L)				Daily yield (L)			
	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Early	11.2	5	0.5	36.6	27.1	9.7	6.9	96.2
Mid	7.3	4	0.3	37.6	17.8	6.6	3.9	59.9
Late	5.5	3.7	0.3	29	13.3	5.4	2.4	48.2
All combined	8	4.9	0.3	37.6	19.4	9.4	2.4	96.2

Table S3. Additional information from the medicines used in simulation scenarios S13. Information was translated with the large language model ChatGPT v2 (OpenAI, <https://openai.com/chat>).

Medicine	Market authorization holder	Dosage form	Excipients	Dosing
Engemycin® vet. Injektionsvätska, lösning 100 mg/ml (Engemycin® vet. Injection solution, 100 mg/ml)	MSD Animal Health Sweden	Injektionsvätska, lösning. (Injection solution)	Natriumformaldehydsulfoxylas, magnesiumoxid , povidon, aminoetanol, vatten för injektionsvätskor till 1 ml. (Sodium formaldehyde sulfoxylate, magnesium oxide, povidone, ethanolamine, water for injections up to 1 ml)	Maximalt rekommenderad volym som kan ges på samma injektionsställe: 20 ml för nötkreatur , 10 ml för får och svin. Upprepad dosering skall ges på olika injektionsställen. Intravenösa injektioner administreras långsamt under minst en minut. För att säkerställa rätt dosering skall kroppsvikten kontrolleras så noga som möjligt för att undvika underdosering. (Maximum recommended volume per injection site: 20 ml for cattle, 10 ml for sheep and pigs. Repeat doses should be administered at different injection sites. Intravenous injections should be administered slowly over at least one minute. To ensure correct dosing, body weight should be determined as accurately as possible to avoid underdosing.)
ENGEMYCINE 10%, oplossing voor injectie voor runderen, schapen en varkens (ENGEMYCINE 10%, solution for injection for cattle, sheep, and pigs)	Intervet Nederland B.V.	Oplossing voor injectie. (Solution for injection)	Natriumformaldehydesulfoxyla Magnesiumoxide Povidone Ethanolamine Water voor injecties (Sodium formaldehyde sulfoxylate, magnesium oxide, povidone, ethanolamine, water for injections)	Maximaal injectievolume per injectieplaats: Grote dieren: 20 ml. Kleine dieren: 5 – 10 ml. Bij herhaalde toediening niet dezelfde injectieplaats gebruiken. Teneinde een juiste dosering te berekenen, dient het lichaamsgewicht zo nauwkeurig mogelijk te worden bepaald. Dit om onderdosering te vermijden. (Maximum injection volume per injection site: Large animals: 20 ml. Small animals: 5 – 10 ml. Do not use the same injection site for repeated administrations. To calculate the correct dosage, body weight must be determined as accurately as possible to avoid underdosing.)
Vetroxy LA 200 mg/ml oplossing voor injectie voor runderen, schapen en varkens (Vetroxy LA 200 mg/ml solution for injection for cattle, sheep, and pigs)	Bimeda Animal Health Limited	Oplossing voor injectie. Een heldere amberkleurige oplossing. (Solution for injection. A clear amber-colored solution.)	Natriumformaldehyde sulfoxyla dihydraat ; Magnesiumoxide , licht ; Dimethylacetamide ; Dinatriumedetaat ; Ethanolamine (voor pH-aanpassing) ; Geconcentreerd zoutzuur (voor pH-aanpassing) ; Water voor injecties (Sodium formaldehyde sulfoxylate dihydrate, light magnesium oxide, dimethylacetamide, disodium edetate, ethanolamine (for pH adjustment), concentrated hydrochloric acid (for pH adjustment), water for injections)	De aanbevolen dosering is 20 mg/kg lichaamsgewicht (d.w.z. 1 ml per 10 kg lichaamsgewicht) toegediend door middel van diepe intramusculaire injectie. Maximaal toe te dienen volume per injectieplek: Runderen : 20 ml (The recommended dosage is 20 mg/kg body weight (i.e., 1 ml per 10 kg body weight), administered via deep intramuscular injection. Maximum volume to be administered per injection site: Cattle: 20 ml.)
GEOMYCINEJECT 100 mg/ml (GEOMYCINEJECT 100 mg/ml)	Dopharma Research B.V.	Oplossing voor injectie.	Benzylalcohol 10 µl Natriumformaldehydesulfoxyla dihydraat Magnesiumchloride	Maximaal injectievolume per injectieplaats: - volwassen rund: 15 ml.

		(Solution for injection)	Polyvidone 12 Polyvidone 17 Ethanolamine Water voor injectie (Benzyl alcohol 10 µl, sodium formaldehyde sulfoxylate dihydrate, magnesium chloride, polyvidone 12, polyvidone 17, ethanolamine, water for injection)	(Maximum injection volume per injection site: - Adult cattle: 15 ml.)
OXTRA DD 100 mg/ml oplossing voor injectie voor runderen, schapen, varkens, paarden, honden en katten. (OXTRA DD 100 mg/ml solution for injection for cattle, sheep, pigs, horses, dogs, and cats)	Fatro S.p.A.	Oplossing voor injectie. Heldere gele tot bruine oplossing. (Solution for injection. A clear yellow to brown-yellow solution.)	Povidon K12 Ethanolamine Licht magnesiumoxide Natriumformaldehydesulfoxylaat Zoutzuur (10% verdund) Water voor injecties (Povidone K12, ethanolamine, light magnesium oxide, sodium formaldehyde sulfoxylate, hydrochloric acid (10% diluted), water for injections)	Not available

SI Figures

Figure S11: The milking interval distribution (A) in the simulated population of 5000 cows. In B, the milk yield per milking as determined by milking frequency (per day) and lactation stage (early, mid, late).

Figure S12: Global sensitivity analysis of milk volume model. Estimation of Sobol' total sensitivity indices are presented in dark blue and estimation of the Sobol' first-order indices in steel blue. Plots are faceted on time (top) and volumes samples from specific compartments at different lactation stages (right).

Figure S13: The bias in the fitted milk data.

Figure S14: The daily yield per milking as determined by milking frequency (per day) and lactation stage (early, mid, late and all three combined). Data summarized from the MonteCarlo simulation of 5000 individuals.

Figure S15. Milk concentrations of 1000 simulated individuals receiving oxytetracycline IV and/or IM, milked with an 8:16 milking interval, and dosing immediately at start of the shortest milking interval. Mean (black line), 5 and 95% (grey lines) represent simulated data. Observed data (blue dots) in A were digitized from Mevius et al 1986¹, and B – D were digitized from the supplementary information in Tardiveau et al². Digitized data were mean values after dosing of several long-acting formulations (A) or mean with upper and lower bars from the standard deviation (B – D). Scenarios (S04 – S07) are described in further detail in Table 3.

Figure S16. Effect of lactation stage, dosing time and milking interval on the withdrawal time of oxytetracycline after once dosing of 10 mg/kg IM. Visualized here are the 95% percentile milk concentration of 1000 simulated individuals per scenario (Scen). Dotted blue line indicates the maximum residue limit of oxytetracycline in milk (MRL; 0.1 mg/L).

Figure S17. The volumes milked and percentage oxytetracycline excreted to milk at 120h after dosing. Numbers in labels on top of graphs denote the subscenario, while the second label shows either the lactation stage (top row) or dosing time (bottom row). Top row shows the scenarios where dose is administered at start of milking before short milking interval are shown (Sx.02, Sx.03, Sx.04). Bottom row shows the percentage excreted to milk when the dosing time was differed. Note that all cows are always milked at 08:00 (start of short milking interval).

Figure S18. Simulated 95th percentile milk concentrations (dots) after clinically relevant dosing regimens (S13, subscenarios in given in grey figure labels). Dosing is noted with the black arrows, where numbers above arrows represent the administered dose in mg/kg. Grey dashed line shows the maximum residue limit (MRL), while grey dotted line represents the calculated end of withdrawal period. End of withdrawal period is determined as the first whole day after last dosing since milk concentration went below MRL.

SI Milk volume model code

\$PROB //

- Author : Ilse R. Dubbelboer
- Final date : August 2024
- Structure : Milk volume in udder and udder compartments

[PARAM] @annotated //model parameters

// Milking parameters

Mtime01 : 0 : time at which first milking of day occurs, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime02 : 0 : time at which second milking of day occurs, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime03 : 0 : time at which third milking of day occurs, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime04 : 0 : time at which fourth milking of day occurs, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime05 : 0 : time at which fifth milking of day occurs, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime06 : 0 : time at which sixth milking of day occurs, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime07 : 0 : time at which seventh milking of day occurs, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime08 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime09 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime10 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime11 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime12 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime13 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime14 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime15 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime16 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime17 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime18 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime19 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime20 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime21 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime22 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mtime23 : 0 : Milking time x, if not then 0 (h)
Mduration : 6 : time duration of milking event (min)

kAlv2Cis : 0.09: milk transfer between alv to cis (h-1)
kmilkprodE : 0.5 : milk production rate early stage (h-1)
kmilkprodM : 0.5 : milk production rate mid stage (h-1)
kmilkprodL : 0.5 : milk production rate late stage (h-1)
AlvMaxE : 10 : max volume alveoli early stage (L)
AlvMaxM : 10 : max volume alveoli mid stage (L)
AlvMaxL : 10 : max volume alveoli late stage (L)
CisMaxE : 5 : max volume cistern early stage (L)
CisMaxM : 5 : max volume cistern mid stage (L)
CisMaxL : 5 : max volume cistern late stage (L)
AlvMin : 0.5 : minimum volume in alveoli (L)
CisMin : 0.01: minimum volume in cistern (L)
HalfLives : 6 : number of half-lives for emptying (-)

\$MAIN //

int day = TIME/24; // the number of days
double dayhr = TIME-day*24; // the time during the day, each day has 24h.
double kem = log(2)*HalfLives/ (Mduration/60); // time in hrs. calculate the halflife based on the
length of the milking period
double switch = 0; // the switch that turns on (1) milk production and turns off (0) the elimination in
between milkings, and vice versa during milking.

if((dayhr >= Mtime01 && dayhr <= (Mtime01+Mduration/60) && Mtime01 >0)|
(dayhr >= Mtime02 && dayhr <= (Mtime02+Mduration/60) && Mtime02 >0)|

```

(dayhr >= Mtime03 && dayhr<= (Mtime03+Mduration/60) && Mtime03 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime04 && dayhr<= (Mtime04+Mduration/60) && Mtime04 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime05 && dayhr<= (Mtime05+Mduration/60) && Mtime05 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime06 && dayhr<= (Mtime06+Mduration/60) && Mtime06 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime07 && dayhr<= (Mtime07+Mduration/60) && Mtime07 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime08 && dayhr<= (Mtime08+Mduration/60) && Mtime08 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime09 && dayhr<= (Mtime09+Mduration/60) && Mtime09 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime10 && dayhr<= (Mtime10+Mduration/60) && Mtime10 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime11 && dayhr<= (Mtime11+Mduration/60) && Mtime11 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime12 && dayhr<= (Mtime12+Mduration/60) && Mtime12 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime13 && dayhr<= (Mtime13+Mduration/60) && Mtime13 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime14 && dayhr<= (Mtime14+Mduration/60) && Mtime14 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime15 && dayhr<= (Mtime15+Mduration/60) && Mtime15 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime16 && dayhr<= (Mtime16+Mduration/60) && Mtime16 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime17 && dayhr<= (Mtime17+Mduration/60) && Mtime17 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime18 && dayhr<= (Mtime18+Mduration/60) && Mtime18 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime19 && dayhr<= (Mtime19+Mduration/60) && Mtime19 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime20 && dayhr<= (Mtime20+Mduration/60) && Mtime20 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime21 && dayhr<= (Mtime21+Mduration/60) && Mtime21 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime22 && dayhr<= (Mtime22+Mduration/60) && Mtime22 >0 )|
(dayhr >= Mtime23 && dayhr<= (Mtime23+Mduration/60) && Mtime23 >0 )) { switch = 1;
    } else {
        switch =0;
    }

```

// INITIAL values of the milk compartments.

ValvdxE_0 = AlvMin;

VcisdxE_0 = CisMin;

ValvdxM_0 = AlvMin;

VcisdxM_0 = CisMin;

ValvdxL_0 = AlvMin;

VcisdxL_0 = CisMin;

//\$INIT @annotated

\$CMT @annotated

ValvdxE: volume alveolar milk (L)

VcisdxE: volume cisternal milk (L)

VmilkedE : volume milked during milking, gives daily yield (L)

ValvdxM: volume alveolar milk (L)

VcisdxM: volume cisternal milk (L)

VmilkedM : volume milked during milking, gives daily yield (L)

ValvdxL: volume alveolar milk (L)

VcisdxL: volume cisternal milk (L)

VmilkedL : volume milked during milking, gives daily yield (L)

\$ODE //

double QalvProdE = kmilkprodE*abs(switch-1)*((AlvMaxE-ValvdxE)/AlvMaxE)*ValvdxE; // becomes L/h, rate describing milk production in alveoli, at early stage lactation

double QalvElimE = (ValvdxE-AlvMin)*kem*switch; // becomes L/h, rate describing milk elimination during milking from alveoli, at early stage lactation

double QAlv2CisE = kAlv2Cis*abs(switch-1)*((ValvdxE-AlvMin))*((CisMaxE-VcisdxE)/CisMaxE);
// becomes L/h, rate describing the transfer rate of milk from alveoli to cistern, at early stage
double QcisElimE = (VcisdxE-CisMin)*kem*switch; // becomes L/h, rate describing milk elimination
during milking from cistern, at early stage lactation

double QalvProdM = kmilkprodM*abs(switch-1)*((AlvMaxM-ValvdxM)/AlvMaxM)*ValvdxM; //
becomes L/h, rate describing milk production in alveoli, at mid stage lactation
double QalvElimM = (ValvdxM-AlvMin)*kem*switch; // becomes L/h, rate describing milk
elimination during milking from alveoli, at mid stage lactation
double QAlv2CisM = kAlv2Cis*abs(switch-1)*((ValvdxM-AlvMin))*((CisMaxM-
VcisdxM)/CisMaxM); // becomes L/h, rate describing the transfer rate of milk from alveoli to cistern,
at mid stage
double QcisElimM = (VcisdxM-CisMin)*kem*switch; // becomes L/h, rate describing milk
elimination during milking from cistern, at mid stage lactation

double QalvProdL = kmilkprodL*abs(switch-1)*((AlvMaxL-ValvdxL)/AlvMaxL)*ValvdxL; //
becomes L/h, rate describing milk production in alveoli, at late stage lactation
double QalvElimL = (ValvdxL-AlvMin)*kem*switch; // becomes L/h, rate describing milk
elimination during milking from alveoli, at late stage lactation
double QAlv2CisL = kAlv2Cis*abs(switch-1)*((ValvdxL-AlvMin))*((CisMaxL-VcisdxL)/CisMaxL);
// becomes L/h, rate describing the transfer rate of milk from alveoli to cistern, at late stage
double QcisElimL = (VcisdxL-CisMin)*kem*switch; // becomes L/h, rate describing milk elimination
during milking from cistern, at late stage lactation

dxdt_ValvdxE = QalvProdE-QAlv2CisE-QalvElimE; // Volume in alveoli over time, at early stage
lactation
dxdt_VcisdxE = QAlv2CisE-QcisElimE; // Volume in cistern over time, at early stage lactation
dxdt_VmilkedE = QalvElimE+QcisElimE; // Volume milked from alveoli and cistern, at early stage
lactation

dxdt_ValvdxM = QalvProdM-QAlv2CisM-QalvElimM; // Volume in alveoli over time, at mid stage
lactation
dxdt_VcisdxM = QAlv2CisM-QcisElimM; // Volume in cistern over time, at mid stage lactation
dxdt_VmilkedM = QalvElimM+QcisElimM; // Volume milked from alveoli and cistern, at mid
stage lactation

dxdt_ValvdxL = QalvProdL-QAlv2CisL-QalvElimL; // Volume in alveoli over time, at late stage
lactation
dxdt_VcisdxL = QAlv2CisL-QcisElimL; // Volume in cistern over time, at late stage lactation
dxdt_VmilkedL = QalvElimL+QcisElimL; // Volume milked from alveoli and cistern, at late stage
lactation

\$TABLE

capture VmilKE = ValvdxE+VcisdxE; // total milk volume in udder, at early stage
capture ValvAvailE = ValvdxE-AlvMin; //available milk for milking in alveoli, at early stage
capture VcisAvailE = VcisdxE-CisMin; //available milk for milking in cistern, at early stage
capture VmilkavailableE = ValvAvailE+VcisAvailE; //total available milk for milking in udder, at
early stage
capture RAlvCisE = ValvAvailE/VcisAvailE; // ratio available milk in udder compartments, at early
stage
capture AlvPerceE = (ValvAvailE)/VmilkavailableE * 100; // percentage of available milk in alveoli, at
early stage
capture CisPerceE = (VcisAvailE)/VmilkavailableE * 100; // percentage of available milk in cistern, at
early stage
capture ResidualMilKE = AlvMin+CisMin; // Volume of milk which is not removed from udder during
milking, at early stage

```
capture VmilkM = ValvdxM+VcisdxM;  
capture ValvAvailM = ValvdxM-AlvMin;  
capture VcisAvailM = VcisdxM-CisMin;  
capture VmilkavailableM = ValvAvailM+VcisAvailM;  
capture RAlvCisM = ValvAvailM/VcisAvailM;  
capture AlvPercM = (ValvAvailM)/VmilkavailableM * 100;  
capture CisPercM = (VcisAvailM)/VmilkavailableM * 100;  
capture ResidualMilkM = AlvMin+CisMin;
```

```
capture VmilkL = ValvdxL+VcisdxL;  
capture ValvAvailL = ValvdxL-AlvMin;  
capture VcisAvailL = VcisdxL-CisMin;  
capture VmilkavailableL = ValvAvailL+VcisAvailL;  
capture RAlvCisL = ValvAvailL/VcisAvailL;  
capture AlvPercL = (ValvAvailL)/VmilkavailableL * 100;  
capture CisPercL = (VcisAvailL)/VmilkavailableL * 100;  
capture ResidualMilkL = AlvMin+CisMin;
```

\$CAPTURE

switch

dayhr

day